

$^{17}\text{O}/^{18}\text{O}$ ratio in post-AGB sources: canonical and non-canonical populations

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The mass of the stars is one of the most elusive yet important parameters determining the stellar evolution. Even masses for binary systems depend on the distance to the target. For low-to-intermediate mass stars, between 0.8 and 8 M_{\odot} , we can determine the initial mass of the star from the $^{17}\text{O}/^{18}\text{O}$ after the first dredge-up. This has been used in AGB stars with some success (de Nutte et al. 2017). Other abundance ratios, such C/O and N/O, can also be used to determine the mass of the star but their values depend on the status of the object along the AGB evolution.

However, for post-AGB stars, we can safely use both methods to check their consistency: $^{17}\text{O}/^{18}\text{O}$ ratio does not change along the AGB and post-AGB evolution, and C/O and N/O should reflect their final values. However the results from the literature are far from being conclusive. According to standard nucleosynthesis and stellar evolution models, we can divide post-AGB stars in three categories. O-rich stars with C/O < 1 and $^{17}\text{O}/^{18}\text{O}$, which correspond to stars up to 1.5 M_{\odot} . C-rich stars with C/O > 1 and $^{17}\text{O}/^{18}\text{O}$ between 1 and 4, which correspond to stars between 1.5 and 4 M_{\odot} . And finally, stars with masses between 4 and 8 M_{\odot} (also known as N-rich) experience Hot Bottom Burning, resulting in C/O < 1, very large values of the $^{17}\text{O}/^{18}\text{O}$ ratio, and enhanced N abundances.

To the right we show the status of the situation before we started this project. There were a number of O-rich sources (black names), M1-92 and some "Water Fountains" (the youngest O-rich post-AGB sources) that unexpectedly show $^{17}\text{O}/^{18}\text{O} > 1$ which is typical of C-rich sources. In addition there is a C-rich post-AGB, 89 Her, with a too low $^{17}\text{O}/^{18}\text{O}$ ratio (below 0.3).

This is why we initiated a project for the determination of C/O and $^{17}\text{O}/^{18}\text{O}$ ratios in additional post-AGN sources. Northern sources would be observed with the IRAM 30m (PI J. Alcolea) while southern sources would be observed with ALMA (PI T. Khouri). Here we present the IRAM 30m results and an update on the statistics after these results and those for 4 sources observed with ALMA (Khouri et al. 2024, in prep.).

• Frosty Leo	O-rich	^{28}SiO ^{13}SiO SO SO_2 H_2S HCN	$^{17}\text{O}/^{18}\text{O} = 1.1 \pm 0.1$	$^{13}\text{CO}/\text{C}^{17}\text{O} = 160 \pm 7$	
• Z02229+6808	C-rich	SiO ^{13}CS SiS SiC_2 $\text{H}^{12/13}\text{CN}$ HC_3N HC_5N HNC ^{13}CN C_3N SiC_2 CH_3CN C_2H C_4H	$^{17}\text{O}/^{18}\text{O} = 0.5 \pm 0.04$	$= 40 \pm 3$	
• IRAS 17436+5005	O-rich	SiO	$^{17}\text{O}/^{18}\text{O} = 0.24 \pm 0.02$	$= 110 \pm 7$	
• IRAS 19475+3119	$^{17}\text{O}/^{18}\text{O} = \dots$	> 90	
• IRAS 19500-1709	C-rich	HCN	$^{17}\text{O}/^{18}\text{O} = 0.66 \pm 0.05$	$= 40 \pm 2$	
• IRAS 21282+5050	C-rich	HCN HCO^+	$^{17}\text{O}/^{18}\text{O} = 0.15 \pm 0.02$	$= 18 \pm 2$	
• IRAS 22272+5435	C-rich	SiO SiC_2 $\text{H}^{12/13}\text{CN}$ $\text{HN}^{12/13}\text{C}$ HCO^+ HC_3N C_2H C_4H	$^{17}\text{O}/^{18}\text{O} = 0.30 \pm 0.04$	$= 55 \pm 5$	
• IRAS 23304+6147	C-rich	SiC_2 $\text{H}^{12/13}\text{CN}$ HNC HC_3N C_3N ^{13}CN C_{24}H	$^{17}\text{O}/^{18}\text{O} = 0.8 \pm 0.1$	$= 13 \pm 1$	
• IRAS 23321+6545	C-rich	SiS $\text{H}^{12/13}\text{CN}$ HNC HC_3N CH_3CN SiC_2	$^{17}\text{O}/^{18}\text{O} = 4.1 \pm 0.5$	$= 2.2 \pm 0.1$	
• CRL 618	C-rich	SiS SiC_2 $\text{H}^{12/13}\text{CN}$ $\text{H}^{12/13}\text{CO}^+$ $\text{HN}^{12/13}\text{C}$ ^{13}CN HC_3N HC_5N HC_7N CH_3CN H_2CO C_3N ...	$^{17}\text{O}/^{18}\text{O} = 1.7 \pm 0.2$	$= 6 \pm 0.1$	
• CRL 2688	C-rich	SiO SiS SiC_2 $\text{H}^{12/13}\text{CN}$ HCO^+ $\text{HN}^{12/13}\text{C}$ C_2H HC_3N ^{13}CS ^{13}CN NaCN $\text{c-C}_3\text{H}_2$	$^{17}\text{O}/^{18}\text{O} = 1.25 \pm 0.01$	$= 8.5 \pm 0.1$	
• NGC 6781	PN	...	$^{17}\text{O}/^{18}\text{O} = \dots$	> 5	
• NGC 7027	young PN	C-rich	$\text{H}^{12/13}\text{CN}$ HNC $\text{c-C}_3\text{H}_2$ N_2H^+ $\text{HC}^{16/17/18}\text{O}^+$ H^{13}CO^+	$^{17}\text{O}/^{18}\text{O} = 2.9 \pm 0.1$	$= 5.3 \pm 0.1$
• CRL 2477	S-type AGB	C-rich	SiO SiS SiC_2 ^{13}CS $\text{H}^{12/13}\text{CN}$ $\text{HN}^{12/13}\text{C}$ C_2H HC_3N ...	$^{17}\text{O}/^{18}\text{O} = 7.6 \pm 1.8$	$= 18.0 \pm 0.5$
• AFGL 2343	post-RSG	O-rich	^{28}SiO HCN SO H_2S	$^{17}\text{O}/^{18}\text{O} = 0.29 \pm 0.01$	$= 42 \pm 1$

In the IRAM 30m project we simultaneously observe the J=2-1 lines of ^{13}CO , C^{18}O , and C^{17}O in 10 new sources, 3 calibrators and 2 control sources. We also observe 8 GHz at 3mm for the detection of species typical of C-rich / O-rich chemistry. The $^{17}\text{O}/^{18}\text{O}$ ratio is directly derived from the $\text{C}^{17}\text{O}/\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ intensity ratio and a small correction factor. The C/O ratio is estimated from the detection / non-detection of C-bearing / O-bearing species. The summary of the results is given in the table above. Examples of the obtained spectra for Z02229+6808 and CRL 618 are shown in the left top and bottom panels respectively.

In the panel to the right we summarise the status of the abundance ratios and initial stellar mass in post-AGB stars after our IRAM 30m results and 4 additional southern sources observed with ALMA (Khouri et al. 2024, in prep.). We already have data for 30 sources, 15 O-rich and 15 C-rich.

For the O-rich stars, we have 8 canonical sources ($^{17}\text{C}/^{18}\text{O} < 1$, those in the blue box), and 7 non-canonical with $^{17}\text{C}/^{18}\text{O} > 1$. This implies that they are too massive to remain O-rich by the end of the AGB. We suggest that these sources had an interrupted AGB evolution which prevented them to turn into C-rich. This interruption may result of common-envelope or similar events (as suggested for M1-92 by Alcolea et al. 2007 and 2022), which aligns with the theories of formation of bipolar pre-planetary nebulae. However metallicity issues can not be discarded yet.

For the C-rich sources, we also have 8 canonical ones if we extend the $^{17}\text{C}/^{18}\text{O}$ ratio up to 8 (twice the maximum value predicted by models). As for the 7 non-canonical ones, with $^{17}\text{C}/^{18}\text{O} < 1$, possible explanations are that these targets are extrinsic C-stars or that they are ^{17}O poor C-stars. Surprisingly we do not find N-rich pre-PN, for which C^{18}O should be undetectable.

(a) Alcolea et al. (2024, in prep); (b) Gallardo Cava et al. (2022)
(c) Sanchez Contreras et al. (priv. comm.)
(d) Khouri et al. (2021); (e) Khouri et al. (2024, in prep)
(f) Masa et al. (2024, in prep); (g) Velilla et al. (2024, in prep)